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HYPERTENSION: CAUSES AND PHARMACEUTICAL ISSUES

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ABSTRACT

Hypertension (High blood pressure) is defined as a condition in which the arteries have persistently elevated blood pressure. Blood pressure is the force of blood against the blood vessel walls. If the pressure is high then heart has harden to pump. Hypertension may also lead to damaged organs, and also cause severe illnesses like kidney failure (renal), heart failure etc. The normal level for blood pressure is 120/80, here 120 represent the systolic pressure (maximum pressure in the arteries) and 80 represent the diastolic pressure (minimum pressure in the arteries). The blood pressure of 140/90 or above is considered hypertension. There are various major causes of hypertension like obesity, lack of physical activity, deficiency of vitamin D, insufficient calcium, potassium and magnesium consumption, chronic kidney disease, aging etc. In this article, focus is on the various types of hypertension, causes of hypertension, pathophysiology of hypertension and antihypertensive drug therapy. The choice of specific drug therapy is depend upon safety, efficacy and cost.

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INTRODUCTION

Hypertension is a very common disorder, particularly past middle age. It is not a disease in itself, but is an important risk factor for cardiovascular mortality. Hypertension also increases the risk of cerebral and renal events. Quality of life during the treatment of hypertension is an important health issue because many patients will discontinue their therapy due to side-effects. So, poor compliance with therapy, would lead to less outcome. In hypertension, majority of cases are of essential (primary) hypertension. In the primary hypertension cause is not known. High blood pressure is a chronic medical condition in which the blood pressure in the arteries is elevated. Many antihypertensive drugs are used to treat hypertension i.e high blood pressure. Antihypertensive drugs are used to control the various complications of high blood pressure like myocardial infarction and stroke. Mostly used antihypertensive drugs are belonging to the class of calcium channel blockers, ACE inhibitors, thiazide diuretics and beta blockers.

TYPES OF HYPERTENSION

PRIMARY HYPERTENSION:

It is also known as essential or idiopathic hypertension, affecting 95% of population. In this type of hypertension, cause is unknown and diagnosed after a doctor notices that blood pressure is high. Primary hypertension shows no symptoms, but people may experience frequent headaches, dizziness, tiredness and nose bleeding. Obesity, smoking, diet, heredity and alcohol play important role in primary hypertension.

MECHANISMS IN PRIMARY HYPERTENSION:

Many patho-physiological mechanisms contribute their role to the development of primary hypertension. It includes: 1) Genetics 2) High salt intake 3) Low physical activity 4) Obesity 5) Insulin resistance 6) Renin – angiotensin system 7) Sympathetic nervous system. [6]

SECONDARY HYPERTENSION:

In the secondary hypertension cause is known and affecting less population (2-3%). Major cause of secondary hypertension is an abnormality in the arteries which supply blood to the kidneys. There are various causes of secondary hypertension. [7]

- 1) Endocrine causes: It includes Cushing's syndrome, Acromegaly, Hyperparathyroidism, Conn's syndrome etc.
- 2) Renal causes: It includes Diabetic nephropathy, polycystic kidney disease, Glomerulonephritis, Renal artery stenosis.
- 3) Other causes: It includes airway obstruction, Abnormalities in hormone, Adrenal glands tumour, Thyroid disease, High amount of salt and alcohol consumption, Acute stress. Some drugs like Ibuprofen and Pseudoephedrine (over-the-counter medications) are also responsible for such type of hypertension.

SOME OTHER ADDITIONAL HYPERTENSION TYPES:

ISOLATED SYSTOLIC HYPERTENSION:

Blood pressure is recorded in two numbers 1) The Upper number is the systolic pressure, and this pressure is occurring during the heartbeat. 2) The Lower number is the diastolic pressure, and this pressure occurs when heart is resting between beats. For normal people, blood pressure is less than 120/80 mm Hg. But in case of isolated systolic hypertension, the systolic pressure rises above 140 and diastolic pressure stays near the normal range i.e below 90. Isolated systolic hypertension caused due to the loss of elasticity in the arteries and very much common in people having the age of 65 or over the age of 65. For the old people, systolic pressure is more important than the diastolic pressure to cause cardiovascular diseases.

RESISTANT HYPERTENSION:

Resistant hypertension occurs in the patients which require three medications to control blood pressure. If doctor has prescribed three different types of antihypertensive drugs to control blood pressure and BP is still very high, then these patients have resistant hypertension. Resistant hypertension is very common in older people, obese people, female, African American and the patients have suffering from diabetes or kidney disease. [8-9]

MALIGNANT HYPERTENSION:

Malignant hypertension is very rare type and occurs in one percent of population. If blood pressure rises very quickly and diastolic pressure goes above 130mm Hg, then this condition called malignant hypertension. Malignant hypertension is very common in adults, African- American men and women having pregnancy toxemia. It includes various symptoms like blurred vision, chest pain, confusion, numbness in the arms, numbness in legs and headache.

There are also other types of hypertension like white coat hypertension and labile hypertension. The labile hypertension means blood pressure that changes over time and it is very common in everyone. [10]

WHITE COAT HYPERTENSION:

White coat hypertension also called as 'Office hypertension or Isolated clinical hypertension'. White coat hypertension is defined as the blood pressure which is higher than normal in medical environment, but when people perform their daily activities the blood pressure is normal. [11-13]

The 2013 European Society of hypertension guidelines recommend that if white coat hypertension is not causes any cardiovascular risk factors to the patients then they should be treated with lifestyle changes. But if white coat hypertension causes cardiovascular risk because of organ damage or metabolic abnormalities then they should be treated with both antihypertensive drug and lifestyle changes. [14]

CLASSIFICATION OF CLINIC BLOOD PRESSURE LEVELS IN ADULTS [15]

CATEGORY	SYSTOLIC (mmHg)	DIASTOLIC (mmHg)
Optimal stage	<120	<80
Normal stage	120-129	80-84
High –normal stage	130-139	85-89
Mild hypertension	140-159	90-99
Moderate hypertension	160-179	100-109
Severe hypertension	>180	>110
Isolated systolic hypertension	>140	<90

CAUSES OF HYPERTENSION: [16]

- Blood pressure generally increases with age in both male and female.
- High body weight is also the cause of hypertension.
- Smoking: It produces nicotine and carbon monoxide which are vasoconstrictor and cause hypertension.
- Alcohol consumption is also cause hypertension.
- Salt consumption (more than 7-10 g per day) cause hypertension.
- Chronic kidney disease.
- Insufficient calcium, potassium and magnesium consumption.

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF HYPERTENSION: [17]**Heredity:**

Hypertension mostly caused by the interaction of environmental factors, demographic factors and genetic factors.

Water and Sodium Retention:

If we take more concentration of sodium then it causes water retention. Some people are sodium (Na) sensitive and some demographics are associated with "salt sensitivity" i.e Obesity, increasing age, people with diabetes, renal disease and African American.

Stress and increased sympathetic nervous system (SNS) activity:

It causes vasoconstriction that leads to increase in heart rate.

Renin – Angiotensin – Aldosterone mechanism:

Renin is an enzyme released by the kidney to maintain body's sodium – potassium balance, fluid volume and BP. When blood pressure decreases, the juxta glomerular (JG) cells secrete renin. Renin acts on plasma protein, angiotensin substrate and converts into Angiotensin I. With the help of angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE) angiotensin is converted into Angiotensin II. Angiotensin II acts on the blood vessels walls and increases the vasoconstriction action. Due to the vasoconstriction, TPR (Total peripheral resistance) will also increase and leads to increase blood pressure. It is the first mechanism.

In second mechanism, angiotensin II also stimulates adrenal cortex. This will cause the high secretion of aldosterone hormone. Aldosterone acts on kidneys and increase the reabsorption of water and sodium (Na). This causes the increase blood volume and leads to increase blood pressure (BP). [18-21]

FLOW CHART OF PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF HYPERTENSION

ANTIHYPERTENSIVE DRUG THERAPY

Antihypertensive drug therapy has been improved in the last 50 years. In 1960, methyldopa, β blockers, thiazide and high ceiling diuretics were used as antihypertensive drugs. Angiotensin II converting enzyme inhibitors and calcium channel blockers were introduced in 1980. Direct renin inhibitor Aliskiren is the latest drug. Safety and tolerability of drugs is very important because hypertension has long term treatment. To provide maximum safety and minimum adverse effects, antihypertensive drugs start with low doses and after that gradually increase where required. [26]

CLASSIFICATION: ANGIOTENSIN II CONVERTING ENZYME (ACE) INHIBITORS [22-23]

DRUGS	DOSE RANGE	TRADE NAME
Ramipril	2.5-10mg daily in one or two doses	Altace, G
Captopril	12.5-50mg twice daily	Capoten, G
Cilazapril	2.5-10mg once daily	Inhibace, G
Benazepril	10-40mg once daily	Lotensin, G
Lisinopril	5-40mg once daily	Prinivil, G
Enalapril	5-40mg daily in one or two doses	Vasotec, G
Trandolapril	1-4mg once daily	Mavik
Quinapril	5-40mg daily in one or two doses	Accupril, G
Fosinopril	10-40mg once daily	Monopril, G

ANGIOTENSIN RECEPTOR BLOCKERS (ARB) [23-25].

DRUGS	DOSE RANGE	TRADE NAME
Losartan	50-100mg once daily	Cozaar, G
Candesartan	8-32mg once daily	Atacand, G
Irbesartan	150-300mg once daily	Avapro, G
Telmisartan	40-80mg once daily	Micardis, G
Valsartan	80-320mg once daily	Diovan, G
Olmesartan	20-40mg once daily	Olmotec
Eprosartan	400-600mg once daily	Teveten

CALCIUM CHANNEL BLOCKERS (CCB) [22-26].

DRUGS	DOSE RANGE	TRADE NAME
Amlodipine	2.5-10mg once daily	Norvasc, G
Nifedipine	30-90mg once daily	Adalat XL, G
Felodipine	2.5-10mg once daily	Plendil
Diltiazem	120-360mg once daily	Cardizem CD, G
Verapamil	80-480mg once daily	Isoptin SR, G

BETA- BLOCKERS [25].

DRUGS	DOSE RANGE	TRADE NAME
Propranolol	40-320mg once daily	Inderal, G
Nadolol	20-320mg once daily	Corgard, G
Timolol	5-30mg once daily	Blocadren, G
Atenolol	25-100mg once daily	Tenormin, G
Metoprolol	50-400mg daily	Lopressor, Betaloc

THIAZIDE DIURETICS [23-25].

DRUGS	DOSE RANGE	TRADE NAME
Chlorthalidone	12.5-25mg daily	G
Hydrochlorothiazide	12.5-25mg once daily	G
Indapamide	1.25-5mg once daily	Lozide, G

DRUG PROFILE (RAMIPRIL) [27-32].

Molecular mass	416.52 g/ml
Description	White, crystalline powder
Solubility	Freely soluble in methanol and sparingly soluble in water
PKa	3.17
Partition coefficient [Log P]	3.41
Protein binding	Protein binding of ramipril is 73% and ramiprilat about 56%
Volume of distribution	Apparent volume of distribution is approx. 1.2 L/kg
Absorption	50-60%
Bioavailability	28%
Biotransformation	Ramipril shows hepatic biotransformation. It is a prodrug and is converted to the active metabolite Ramiprilat by liver esterase enzymes.
Uses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To treat high blood pressure To treat people after recent heart attack
Contraindications	Contraindications for the use of ramipril include angioedema, renal failure, and pregnancy (second and third trimesters).

CONCLUSION

Hypertension puts strain on the heart and its leads to heart disease and coronary artery disease. Maintenance of the healthy lifestyle is very essential for the prevention of high blood pressure, but drug treatment is still very important in people for whom healthy lifestyle is not effective. The angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors are one of the first choice drugs for any type of hypertension (except bilateral renal artery stenosis). Dry cough is the most common side effect of ACE inhibitors. The selection of the appropriate drug therapy is mainly dependent upon the safety, efficacy and cost of the medicine. Effective drug combinations are also given to the patient for better result. Drugs which increase plasma renin activity like vasodilators, calcium channel blockers, ACE inhibitors may be combined with drugs which lower plasma renin activity like β -blockers, clonidine and methyldopa. The future vaccine may also help to the patient for lowering blood pressure up to six months. Researchers have designed a DNA vaccine which helped to lowering blood pressure for up to six months. This DNA vaccine reduced tissue damage to the heart and blood vessels and also has no signs of damage to other organs such as the kidney or liver.

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